

An Analysis of Solute Transport across Aromatic Polyamide Hydrazide Reverse Osmosis Membranes

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The study of solute transport across freshly synthesised high rejecting aromatic polyamide hydrazide reverse osmosis (RO) membranes and the predictability of RO separations obtainable from these membranes are reported. Transport of solute and solvent through RO membranes are analysed as a function of feed molarity, pressure and temperature in terms of pure water permeation constant (A), solute transport parameter ($D_{AM}/K\delta$) and mass transfer coefficient on the high pressure side of the membranes using Kimura-Sourirajan's transport analysis. Experimental separation data for various electrolytes in dilute aqueous media are presented. Reported free energy parameter ($-A \Delta G/RT$), for specific ions are used to predict the separation behaviour for a few 1 : 1 electrolytes.

Wholly aromatic polyamide hydrazides (APAH), a potential high performance material with high thermal stability and mechanical strength, are a class of speciality polymers used in reverse osmosis (RO) applications. They exhibit high degree of selectivity to dissolved salts at moderately high levels of water transport with excellent chemical and radiation stability. The membrane performance of these polymers in RO applications are influenced by several structural and processing variables, such as primary polymer structure (*m/p*-phenylene units), casting solution composition, the extent of solvent evaporation and the rate at which sol-gel phase inversion takes place. Development of a series of polyamide hydrazide class of membranes for RO and ultrafiltration (UF) applications has been reported^{1,2} earlier from this laboratory. The study of solute transport across these high rejecting membranes and the predictability of RO separations obtainable from these membranes is of immense practical interest. The membrane semipermeability with respect to electrolytes is attributed to the strong polar-polar interactions of water molecules with membranes and the inability of the bound water to hydrate the solute ions. The transport of solute and solvent across RO membranes has been generally characterised by solution-diffusion approach, phenomenological coefficients using irreversible thermodynamics, electrochemical and electrokinetic methods and preferential

sorption-capillary flow. The preferential sorption-capillary flow mechanism along with the quantitative expression derived from surface force-pore flow considerations are used in the solute transport analysis, reported in this paper.

Transport equations : The physicochemical criteria governing RO separations is based on preferential sorption at membrane-solution interface. This preferential sorption is a function of solute-solvent-membrane material interactions. These interactions in general arise from ionic, polar and nonpolar character of each of the above components. The preferential sorption and capillary diffusion mechanism combines two distinct factors, namely, the equilibrium effect concerning the preferential sorption of solute and solvent in the immediate vicinity of the membrane surface and the kinetic effect dealing with mobilities of the solute and the solvent through the pores.

The overall transport of solute and solvent across membranes is quantified in terms of basic transport equations³,

$$A = \frac{[PWP]}{M_B S 3600 P} \quad (1)$$

$$N_B = A [P - \pi(X_{A2}) + \pi(X_{A3})] \quad (2)$$

$$= c \left[\frac{D_{AM}}{K\delta} \right] \frac{[1 - X_{A3}]}{X_{A3}} (X_{A2} - X_{A3}) \quad (3)$$

$$= kc \left[(1 - X_{A3}) \right] \ln \frac{X_{A2} - X_{A3}}{X_{A1} - X_{A3}} \quad (4)$$

The quantity A is a measure of the overall porosity of the membrane and corresponds to conditions of zero concentration polarisation and it is independent of any solute under consideration. The parameter $(D_{AM} / K\delta)$ plays the role of mass transfer coefficient with respect to solute transport *through* the membrane and is treated as a single quantity, even though it combines diffusivity of the solute in the membrane phase (D_{AM}), partition coefficient (K) of solute between solution and membrane phases and membrane thickness (δ). Since the solute is concentrated in the boundary solution and diffuses back to the less concentrated feed solution on the high pressure side of the membranes, a mass transfer coefficient (k) which is characteristic of the experimental hydrodynamic conditions prevailing on the high pressure side of the membrane is incorporated for complete system specification.

Results and Discussion

The specification of the membrane sample PAH-1 and PAH-2 in terms of PWP, A , $(D_{AM} / K\delta)$, k , PR and f are given in Table 1. The A , $(D_{AM} / K\delta)$ and k values are obtained from experimental data on PR and

f using the above set of transport equations. The RO performance with respect to sodium chloride solute for various pressures, feed molarities and temperatures for both the membrane systems are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—RO PERFORMANCE FOR DIFFERENT PRESSURES, FEED CONCENTRATION AND TEMPERATURES

Pressure (kPa)	PAH-1			PAH-2		
	PR	f	PWP	PR	f	PWP
4054	42.1	0.977	44.8	35.5	0.984	38.1
5068	47.8	0.980	50.6	41.6	0.986	44.6
6081	54.6	0.982	57.7	47.9	0.987	51.0
7095	60.4	0.985	63.8	54.6	0.990	58.1
Feed molarity = 0.07m, Feed temp. = 28°						
Temp (°C)						
26.5	39.4	0.975	42.2	26.9	0.984	29.9
31.8	51.2	0.980	53.9	41.2	0.984	44.0
37.2	60.7	0.983	63.7	49.4	0.991	52.5
43.8	75.4	0.984	80.3	61.7	0.994	64.6
Feed molarity = 0.07m, Pressure = 4054 kPa						
Feed molarity (m)						
0.07	54.6	0.982	-	47.9	0.987	-
0.154	48.7	0.973	-	42.7	0.982	-
0.360	40.2	0.962	-	35.1	0.974	-
0.450	36.6	0.954	-	31.2	0.969	-
Pressure = 6081 kPa, feed temp. = 28°, membrane area = $15.4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^2$						

It can be seen that both product rate (PR) and solute separation (f) values increase with increase in feed temperature and applied pressure. Product rate and solute separation decrease as the feed concentration increases. With respect to a given solute-solvent system, the membrane is completely specified in terms of A , $(D_{AM} / K\delta)$ and k values. The transport equations developed on the basis of preferential sorption and capillary flow mechanism enables the prediction of RO performance for various feed molarities at a specified pressure, temperature and feed flow conditions based on the above membrane specification data. Such a prediction is possible if A , $(D_{AM} / K\delta)$ and k values obtained for a particular concentration, pressure, temperature and feed flow conditions for a given

TABLE 1—MEMBRANE SPECIFICATION DATA

	PAH-1	PAH-2
Pure water permeability (pwp) $\times 10^3$ kg/h	44.8	39.5
Pure water permeation constant (A) $\times 10^3$ kg/mo ³ H ₂ O/m ² s kPa	1.107	0.975
Solute transport parameter $(D_{AM} / K\delta) \times 10^3$ m/s	1.6	0.72
Product rate (PR) $\times 10^3$ l/h	42.1	35.5
Solute separation factor (f)	0.977	0.984
Membrane area = $15.4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^2$, applied pressure = 4054 kPa; feed molarity (m) = 0.07 NaCl; mass transfer coefficient (k) = $4.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m/s}$.		

solute-solvent system are held valid for the entire range of feed concentrations. Pure water permeations constant and solute transport parameter values are known⁴ to be an exponential function of feed pressure and temperature. The A values decrease with increase in pressure and increase with increase in feed temperature. The values of k are known⁴ to be dependent on feed flow and temperature. The k values increase with increase in feed flow rate and temperature. The solute transport parameter ($D_{AM} / K\delta$) values are reported to be independent of feed concentration. The correlations of A and k values for feed pressure, temperature and feed flow conditions and the constancy of ($D_{AM} / K\delta$) with feed molarity with respect to cellulose acetate membranes is reported³. With respect to aromatic polyamide hydrazide membranes, the variation of A and ($D_{AM} / K\delta$) for various feed pressures and temperatures are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. The predictability of RO performance involves the following steps⁴.

Combining equations (2) and (3),

$$AP - AB(X_{A2} - X_{A3}) = \left[\frac{D_{AM}}{K\delta} \right] c \left[\frac{1 - X_{A3}}{X_{A3}} \right] (X_{A2} - X_{A3}) \quad (5)$$

where B is the proportionality constant between osmotic pressure and mole fraction kPa. Rearranging, we get

$$X_{A2} - X_{A3} = \frac{AP}{AB + \left(\frac{D_{AM}}{K\delta} \right) c \left(\frac{1 - X_{A3}}{X_{A3}} \right)} \quad (6)$$

Fig. 1. Correlation of A and ($D_{AM} / K\delta$) with applied pressure.

Fig. 2. Correlation of ($D_{AM} / K\delta$) with feed molarity

By trial and error, the combinations of X_{A2} and X_{A3} which satisfies the equality of equations (3) and (4) are obtained. This determines the values of N_B . Using the values of X_{A3} and N_B determined above and the known values of X_{A1} , product rate (PR) and solute separation (f) are obtained using the following set of equations,

$$PR = N_B M_A S \times 3600 \left[\frac{1 + M_1(1-f)M_B}{1000} \right] \quad (7)$$

$$f = (X_{A1} - X_{A3}) / X_{A1} \quad (8)$$

The RO performance is predicted for PAH-1 and PAH-2 membranes for various feed molarities in the range 0.154–0.564 at 4054 kPa pressure and 30° temperature. The predicted RO performances are given in Table 3 and are compared with experimental values. It can be seen that reasonably good agreement is obtained for both the membrane samples at lower feed molarities. At higher feed molarities the predicted solute separation is higher than the experimental values. This could be due to the variations of ($D_{AM} / K\delta$) values at higher feed molarities. The experimentally obtained ($D_{AM} / K\delta$) values are found to increase with increase in feed molarities as can be seen in Fig. 3. The studies indicate that the transport equations derived based on preferential sorption and capillary flow mechanism satisfactorily predicts the RO performance in the low concentration range.

Fig. 3. Correlation of $A uw$ and $(D_{AM} / K \delta)$ with feed temperature.

TABLE 3—COMPARISON OF PREDICTED AND OBSERVED RO PERFORMANCE

Membrane	Feed molarity M	Observed		Predicted	
		(PR)	f	(PR)	f
PAH-1	0.07	54.6	0.982	52.3	0.974
	0.154	48.7	0.973	47.4	0.975
	0.248	44.3	0.966	43.2	0.969
	0.360	40.2	0.962	39.4	0.964
	0.450	36.6	0.954	34.7	0.962
PAH-2	0.07	47.9	0.987	46.1	0.981
	0.154	42.7	0.982	41.5	0.978
	0.248	38.6	0.979	37.2	0.976
	0.360	35.1	0.974	34.5	0.974
	0.450	31.2	0.969	30.1	0.971

Applied pressure = 6081 kPa; feed temp. = 28°; membrane area = $15.4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^2$

Predictability of RO performance for various other solutes are obtained by making use of the free energy parameters. The transport of solute and solvent across the membrane is explained by sorption of solute and solvent at the membrane interface and their subsequent diffusion through membrane pores. The different transport rates through membrane barrier observed for different solutes are explained by the differences in the ionic interactions at the membrane solution interfaces. These interactions are quantitatively expressed in terms of applicable free energy parameters for individual ions (denoted by $(-\Delta\Delta G/RT)_i$) for specified interfacial system. The experimental and computational details involved in generating the free energy parameters for

different inorganic and nonionised organic solutes has been discussed elsewhere⁴. The free energy parameter is a differential free energy of hydration between bulk water and bound water. It is dependent on the solute-solvent-membrane material system and is independent of the porous structure of the membranes. With respect to completely ionised inorganic solutes in aqueous solutions, it has been shown that $(D_{AM} / K \delta)$ for any solute is related to the free energy parameter for the constituent ions by the expression,

$$\ln (D_{AM} / K \delta) = \ln c^* + \sum \left(\frac{-\Delta\Delta G_i}{RT} \right) \quad (9)$$

where $\ln c^*$ is a constant and the subscript i represents the ions involved. The quantity $\ln c^*$ is a function of the porous structure of the membrane which can be obtained using experimentally derived values of $\ln (D_{AM} / K \delta)_{\text{NaCl}}$ and data on $(-\Delta\Delta G/RT)$ for Na^+ and Cl^- ions. If data on $(-\Delta\Delta G/RT)_i$ for any other monovalent cations and anions are available, one can then calculate $(D_{AM} / K \delta)$ for solutes involving such ions. The reported⁴ free energy parameter data for some monovalent cations and anions applicable for aromatic polyamide hydrazide are used in our studies (Table 4). RO performance data for various electrolytes with respect to PAH-2 membrane and the experimentally obtained $(D_{AM} / K \delta)$ values are given in Table 5. Comparison of the solute separation obtained experimentally and computed from free energy parameters is given in Table 6. It can be seen that reasonably good

TABLE 4—FREE ENERGY PARAMETERS FOR SOME MONOVALENT CATIONS AND ANIONS^a

Ion	Ionic radius	$(-\Delta\Delta G/RT)_i$
Li^+	0.60	-1.20
Na^+	0.95	-1.35
K^+	1.33	-1.28
Cs^+	0.69	-1.23
NH_4^+	-	-1.33
F	1.36	1.03
Cl	1.81	1.35
NO_3^-	-	2.54
Acetate	-	1.33

^a Ref. 4.

TABLE 5—SEPARATION DATA FOR VARIOUS INORGANIC SOLUTES

Solute	Separation (f)	($D_{AM} / K \delta$) $10^5 \times \text{cm/d}$
Sodium chloride	0.976	1.114
Lithium chloride	0.978	1.01
Potassium chloride	0.981	0.843
Sodium nitrate	0.942	2.775
Sodium fluoride	0.974	1.120
Lithium nitrate	0.964 ^a	1.648
Ammonium nitrate	0.942	2.801
Sodium acetate	0.964	1.663
Ammonium chloride	0.954	2.131

Membrane area (PAH-2) = 15.4 cm²; feed concn. = 0.05 m; pressure applied = 30 bar.

TABLE 6—COMPARISON OF EXPERIMENTAL AND COMPUTED SOLUTE SEPARATION

Solute	$f_{\text{expt.}}$	$f_{\text{calc.}}$
Lithium chloride	0.978	0.972
Potassium chloride	0.981	0.973
Lithium nitrate	0.944	0.932
Sodium fluoride	0.974	0.981
Ammonium chloride	0.9754	0.940
Sodium nitrate	0.954	0.940
Ammonium nitrate	0.942	0.937
Sodium acetate	0.964	0.956

agreement exists between calculated and experimental solute separation data, confirming the validity of the free energy parameters in predicting RO separations.

Conclusions : Reverse osmosis performance of freshly prepared aromatic polyamide hydrazide membranes are reported with respect to sodium chloride solute for various applied pressures, feed molarities and temperatures. The RO performance data are analysed using Kimura-Sourirajan's transport equations based on preferential sorption-capillary flow mechanism. The correlation of pure water permeation constant and solute transport parameter with pressure, temperature and feed molarities are reported. Predictability of RO performance using the above transport equations for various feed molarities at constant pres-

sure and temperature is verified at low concentrations. Deviation from the predicted RO performance was noticed at higher feed concentrations. RO performance data for various solutes are presented and the use of interfacial free energy parameters are verified for predicting RO performance of various solute systems.

Experimental

Synthesis of aromatic polyamide hydrazide polymer has been already reported¹. RO membrane samples were prepared by dissolving 15% (w) of polymer in dimethyl acetamide solvent with 30% (by weight of the polymer) lithium nitrate as additive and casting over a glass plate. The as-cast membranes (thickness around 300 μ) were subjected to partial solvent evaporation at 95–100° under partial vacuum (300 mm) for 20 min (PAH-1) and for 40 min (PAH-2). The nascent films were gelled in demineralised water maintained at ambient temperature. The membranes were used after thorough washing (free of residual solvent and additive). They were tested in a reverse osmosis recirculation test loop under near zero recovery conditions. The feed and permeate samples were analysed by conductance measurements.

Nomenclature

A	Pure water permeability constant, kg mol H ₂ O/m ² s kPa
C	Molar density kg mol/m ³
D_{AB}, D_{AM}	Diffusivity of solute in solvent in membrane phase, m ² /s
f	Solute separation
K	Proportionality constant relating concentration of solute between solution and membrane phases
k	Mass transfer coefficient on high pressure side, m/s
N_B	Solvent flux through the membrane kg mol/m ² s
M_B, M_A	Molecular weight of solvent, solute
P	Applied pressure, kPa
PWP, PR	Pure water permeability and product rate through a given membrane area at a specified pressure, kg/h

S	Membrane area, m^2
X_{A1}, X_{A2}, X_{A3}	Mole fraction of solute in bulk feed, boundary layer and permeate
π	Osmotic pressure, kPa
δ	Membrane thickness, m
$(-\Delta G/RT)_i$	Free energy parameter for a specific ion
$\ln C'$	Factor representing porosity on membrane surface
B	Proportionality constant relating osmotic pressure and mole fraction

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